

Approaches to Total Synthesis of Azasteroids. Part I. A Study of Methods for Introducing Nitrogen at Position 8 of Steroidal Nucleus

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Reaction of unsaturated lactone (VIII) with amines is shown to be a convenient method for introducing nitrogen into the ring system. Hydrogenation of (VIII) has been investigated and stereochemistry of the corresponding saturated lactones (IV and V) delineated.

In connection with a project for total synthesis of 8-azasteroids, we have been studying methods of obtaining polycyclic lactams which on ring-closure can furnish the desired skeleton. A convenient method for lactam synthesis is the reduction of δ -oximino-acids^{1,2} by sodium and ethanol. When the oximino-acid (II) was so reduced, the only isolable product was an amino-acid (III) which could not be cyclised. The failure of cyclisation may be attributed to its unfavourable (*trans*) stereochemistry.

The reaction of ammonia or its derivatives with lactones is another widely used method for synthesising lactams³⁻⁵. In the present series, however, lactones (IV) and (V) failed to react with ammonia and could be recovered unchanged after long reaction periods at room temperature. At 200-50° the *cis*-lactone (IV) furnished an impure nitrogenous liquid which on subsequent lithium aluminium hydride reduction provided the amine (VII) in a poor yield. Under similar conditions, the *trans*-lactone (V) afforded only an untractable tar.

In contrast, the introduction of nitrogen was found to be facile with the corresponding unsaturated lactone (VIII) which at room temperature was allowed to react separately with ammonia and with β -phenethylamine to furnish (IXa) and (IXb), respectively, in excellent yield⁶.

The unusual reactivity of the unsaturated lactone (VIII) prompted us to investigate some of its other properties. Of special interest is its hydrogenation over platinum catalyst. More than one mole (1.7) of hydrogen are consumed and a mixture of two products is obtained. The acidic fraction is identified to be cyclopentane-propionic acid (X) and the neutral fraction has been assigned structure (XI) on the basis of its elemental analysis⁷⁻⁹. The acid

1. Bolt, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1938, 57, 905.
2. McKenna and Tulley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 945.
3. Sugawara *et al.*, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1961, 71, 1341.
4. Bertho and Rodi, *Ber.*, 1959, 92, 221.
5. Ruppe *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1955, 596, 159.
6. Uskokovic and Gut, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 643; *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1959, 42, 2259.
7. Jacobs and Scott, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1930, 87, 401.
8. Turner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 570.
9. Newman and Vander Werf, *ibid.*, 1945, 67, 233.

(X) must arise by direct hydrogenolysis of the vinyl ether bond as both *cis*- and *trans*-saturated lactones (IV and V) have been found to be stable under the conditions of hydrogenation.

The keto-acid (I) was reduced with sodium and ethanol by Hirt¹⁰ to obtain a lactone (V) of unassigned stereochemistry. Sukh Dev and Rai¹¹ reduced the same keto-acid with sodium borohydride to obtain a lactone (IV) which was tentatively assigned a *cis*-structure on the basis of the difficulty in constructing the model of the *trans*-isomer. No comparison with the earlier product was, however, reported. We have repeated both the experiments and found the two lactones to be different. As sodium and ethanol reduction of the keto-acid (I) should furnish thermodynamically more stable *trans*-alcohol¹², the lactone (V) can be assigned a *trans*-structure. This also confirms *cis*-fusion in lactone (IV).

The preponderant formation of a *cis*-alcohol, and subsequently of *cis*-lactone (IV), on sodium borohydride reduction of the keto-acid(I) indicates that 'steric approach control' operates in such reductions of α-alkylated cyclopentanones¹³.

10. Cf. Rapson and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1533.

11. This *Journal*, 1957, 34, 266.

12. Barton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1027.

13. Dauben *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 2679.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Oxocyclopentane-propionic Acid (I).—The keto-acid (I) was obtained by addition of ethyl acrylate to 2-ethoxycarbonylcyclopentanone and subsequent hydrolysis according to the procedure of Sukh Dev and Rai¹¹. An alternative preparation, using acrylonitrile afforded a poorer yield (25%).

Oxime of (I) [II].—A mixture of (I) (10 g.), ethanol (150 ml), 10% KOH solution (80 ml) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (6 g.) was refluxed for 3 hours. After cooling it was made acidic with acetic acid and the solvent removed. The residue was taken in chloroform, washed with water, and evaporated to dryness. Crystallisation (benzene) afforded a colorless solid, m.p. 105-106°. (Found: N, 8.13. $C_8H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 8.18%).

trans-2-Aminocyclopentane-propionic Acid (III).—Sodium metal (20 g.) was added in pieces to a boiling solution of the oxime (II) (5 g.) in ethanol (200 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 30 minutes and made acidic with acetic acid. The solvent was removed and the residue heated for 4 hours under reduced pressure (10 mm) at 180-90°. The organic material was then extracted with chloroform, washed with water, and the solvent removed. Crystallisation from light petroleum (40-60°) furnished colorless needles, m.p. 135-35.5°. (Found: N, 9.08. $C_8H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 8.99%).

cis-3-Oxo-2-oxabicyclo-(4,3,0)nonane (IV).—The lactone (IV) was prepared by sodium borohydride reduction of the keto-acid (I) according to the procedure of Sukh Dev and Rai¹¹; b.p. 122°/2.5 mm, n_D^{24} 1.4820.

trans-3-Oxo-2-oxabicyclo-(4,3,0)nonane (V) was prepared by reduction of (I) with sodium and ethanol according to the procedure of Hirt¹⁰; b.p. 135-40°/17 mm, n_D^{38} 1.4873.

Reaction of Lactone (IV) with Ammonia.—A solution of lactone (IV) (5 g.) in ethanol (50 ml) was cooled to 0° and saturated with dry ammonia. It was then heated at 200-50° for 6 hours in an autoclave. After cooling, the solvent was removed and the residue fractionated to collect a light brown liquid (3 g.); b.p. 135-45°/3mm, n_D^{18} 1.4885.

The foregoing liquid (2 g.) was refluxed and stirred for 10 hours with lithium aluminium hydride (2 g.) in dry ether (100 ml). The excess hydride was decomposed by cautious addition of water (3 ml) while the stirring was continued. The precipitate was removed and the filtrate directly converted into a picrate. Two crystallisations from benzene provided yellow needles, m.p. 168-70°. (Found: N, 15.97. $C_{14}H_{18}O_7N_4$ requires N, 15.81%).

Reaction of lactone (V) with ammonia, carried out in the aforementioned manner, afforded only a polymeric material which could not be distilled.

3-Oxo-2-oxabicyclo-(4,3,0)non-1-ene (VIII) was prepared according to the procedure of Shusherina *et al.*¹⁴. It was found that addition of sodium acetate (0.5 M) to the reaction

* M.p.'s and b.p.'s. are uncorrected. Microanalyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford, and by Shri B. N. Anand, Chemistry Department, Chandigarh.

14. Shusherina *et al.*, *Chem. Abs.*, 1966, 50, 13887.

mixture afforded a superior (80%) yield; b.p. 92-93°/4 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4965. The lactone (VIII) gave the following reactions:

(i) A 5% solution of bromine in CCl_4 was immediately decolorised on adding one drop of the compound.

(ii) On addition of one drop of ammoniacal silver nitrate to a 0.2% solution of the lactone in water, a black precipitate was deposited immediately.

(iii) To a 20% solution of the compound in pyridine was added a saturated solution (3 drops) of sodium nitroprusside, followed by one drop of 10% NaOH solution. An immediate blood-red colour developed which turned purple on addition of HCl (dil.).

3-Oxo-2-azabicyclo-(4,3,0)non-1-ene (IXa).—Dry ammonia was bubbled through a cooled (5°) solution of freshly distilled unsaturated lactone (VIII) (10 g.) in dry ether (50 ml). The solid separating was filtered, washed with ether, and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 80-80.5°. (Found: N, 9.95. $C_8H_{11}ON$ requires N, 10.21%).

Hydrogenation of 3-Oxo-2-azabicyclo-(4,3,0)non-1-ene (IXa).—When a solution of (IXa) (5 g.) in ethanol (50 ml) was shaken over platinum catalyst (0.05 g.) with hydrogen at atmospheric pressure, no absorption was observed. HCl (3 ml) was then added and hydrogenation continued till completion (4 hours). The catalyst was filtered and the solvent removed from the filtrate. The residue was made basic (NaOH) and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried, and evaporated. Distillation of the residue furnished an oil (2.5 g.) boiling over a wide range. It was crystallised twice from light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) as a colorless solid (0.3 g.), m.p. 75-76°. (Found: C, 69.22; H, 9.70; N, 9.71%).

Picrate of this base crystallised from benzene as yellow needles, m.p. 220-21°. (Found: C, 53.49; H, 6.52; N, 11.65%). The analytical results could not be fitted with any simple products expected from hydrogenation of (IXa).

3-Oxo-2-β-phenethylazabicyclo-(4,3,0)non-1-ene (IXb).—A cooled solution (10°) of (VIII) (6.8 g.) in benzene (50 ml) was added dropwise to a cooled solution (10°) of β-phenethylamine (6.8 g.) in benzene (25 ml). The mixture was allowed to stand for 18 hours at room temperature and then extracted with HCl (dil.). The organic layer was washed with water, dried, and the solvent removed. The residue was fractionated to obtain a yellow liquid (8 g.); b.p. 215-18°/2 mm, n_D^{25} 1.5525. (Found: N, 5.35. $C_{16}H_{19}ON$ requires N, 5.80%).

Hydrogenation of the Unsaturated Lactone (VIII).—A solution of (VIII) (5 g.) in ethanol (50 ml) was hydrogenated over platinum catalyst (20 mg.) till the absorption of hydrogen had ceased (1.7 M). The catalyst was filtered and the solvent removed from the filtrate. The residue was taken up in ether and extracted with sodium carbonate solution. The organic layer was washed with water, dried, and the solvent removed. The residue on distillation furnished a colorless liquid (1.4 g.); b.p. 120°/4 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4505 (lit.¹³ b.p. 150°/18 mm, n_D^{19} 1.4514). (Found: C, 64.97; H, 8.54. $C_{10}H_{13}O_2$ requires C, 65.22; H, 8.89%).

The sodium carbonate extract was made acidic and the organic material taken up in ether. The ether layer was washed with water, dried, and the solvent removed. The residue on distillation provided a colorless liquid (3.2 g.); b.p. 122°/5 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4530 (lit.¹⁶ b.p. 131°/6 mm, $n_D^{17.4}$ 1.4594).

The anilide prepared in the usual manner melted at 109-10° (lit.¹⁶ m.p. 110°).

Hydrogenation of Lactones (IV and V).—No absorption was observed when lactones (IV) and (V) were hydrogenated as above. Both the compounds could be recovered unchanged

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16. Barrett *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1065.